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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINYA bearing USN 6SU21AO001 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISHWARYA P K bearing USN 6SU21AO002 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA S VIJAYAN bearing USN 6SU21AO003 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSILAMOL S bearing USN 6SU21AO004 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA APPUKUTTAN bearing USN 6SU21AO005 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHUL B bearing USN 6SU21AO006 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DIV DAS bearing USN 6SU21AO007 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SHANA bearing USN 6SU21AO008 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAWAZ bearing USN 6SU21AO009 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA S bearing USN 6SU21A0010 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOUTHAMI E T bearing USN 6SU21AO011 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOVINDAM RAGHAVENDRA bearing USN 6SU21AO012 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARIS P NAZEER bearing USN 6SU21AO013 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ISHAN K bearing USN 6SU21AO014 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JYOTHIKA M bearing USN 6SU21AO015 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms K P BASIM ANSAF bearing USN 6SU21AO016 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED RAMIL U K bearing USN 6SU21AO017 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUJEEB RAHMAN K B bearing USN 6SU21AO018 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAHLA R S bearing USN 6SU21A0019 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHA ABDUL SALIM bearing USN 6SU21AO020 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAGARLAL A bearing USN 6SU21AO021 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAHANA NOUSHAD K bearing USN 6SU21AO022 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHALBIYA ABBAS bearing USN 6SU21AO023 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRINIDHI S bearing USN 6SU21AO024 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SONA M K bearing USN 6SU21AO025 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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